

FUZZY LOGIC APPLIED IN THE PAPER

Fuzzy logic for proximity of transmission lines:

$$(("dist_trans_lines@1">=1000)*("dist_trans_lines@1"<=1000)*((10000/(10000-1000))-("dist_trans_lines@1"/(10000-1000))))+("dist_trans_lines@1"<1000)$$

Fuzzy logic for proximity of main roads:

$$(("dist_main_roads@1">=1000)*("dist_main_roads@1"<=3000)*((3000/(3000-1000))-("dist_main_roads@1"/(3000-1000))))+("dist_main_roads@1"<1000)$$

Fuzzy logic for proximity of urban areas:

$$(("dist_urb_areas@1">=5000)*("dist_urb_areas@1"<=75000)*((75000/(75000-5000))-("dist_urb_areas@1"/(75000-5000))))+("dist_urb_areas@1"<5000)$$

Fuzzy logic for direct normal irradiance (DNI):

Considering as minimum in Brazil = 1778 Wh/m²/Day and maximum in Brazil = 6465 Wh/m²/Day.

$$(("boolean_dni@1">=1778)*("boolean_dni@1"<=6465)*(("boolean_dni@1"/(6465-1778))-("1778/(6465-1778))))+("boolean_dni@1">6465)$$

Fuzzy logic for ground slope:

$$(("slope@1">=0)*("slope@1"<=30)*((30/(30-0))-("slope@1"/(30-0))))+("slope@1"<0)$$

Fuzzy logic for ground aspect:

$$(("aspect@1">=0)*("aspect@1"<=45)*((45/(45-0))-("aspect@1"/(45-0))))+(("aspect@1"<0)+("aspect@1">360))+(("aspect@1">=315)*("aspect@1"<=360)*(("aspect@1"/(36-315))-("315/(360-315))))$$

Fuzzy Logic for proximity of water and reforestation áreas:

$$(("dist_water_ref@1">=200)*("dist_water_ref@1"<=500)*(("dist_water_ref@1"/(500-200))-("200/(500-200))))+("dist_water_ref@1">500)$$

Cálculo Final do estudo de localização:

$$(("fuzzy_dist_trans_lines@1"*0.3658)+("fuzzy_dist_main_roads@1"*0.15)+("fuzzy_dist_urb_areas@1"*0.0612)+("fuzzy_dni@1"*0.2553)+("fuzzy_slope@1"*0.0781)+("fuzzy_aspect@1"*0.0391)+("fuzzy_dist_water_ref@1"*0.0505)*"boolean_exclusion_areas@1"$$